

Spectrophotometric Investigation of Ti(IV) Complexes of N-Cinnamoyl Phenyl Hydroxylamine

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N-cinnamoyl phenyl hydroxylamine reacts with titanium to form the yellow coloured complexes with metal to ligand ratios 1 : 1 in the acidity range extending from pH 0.5 to 2.5N, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 (metal : ligand) in the acidity ranges of 3-5N and 7-5-9N HCl respectively. All the complexes were extractable into chloroform. The composition of the complexes were established by Job's and molar ratio methods. The stepwise and overall formation constants of all the complexes were determined by extended Yatsimirskii's, Leden's and Harvey Manning's method. For the evaluation of formation constants of 1 : 3 system following Yatsimirskii's method, a computer (IBM 1130) was deployed using FORTRAN Programming. An extractive spectrophotometric method of determination of trace amount of titanium in presence of diverse ions has also been described.

Different aryl hydroxamic acids and their N-phenyl analogues¹⁻⁹ have been in use for about two decades as potential analytical reagents for different metals. But in a very few cases¹⁰⁻¹³, variation of compositions of the complexes at different acidities have been investigated. This paper gives an account of an extractive spectrophotometric investigation of Ti(IV) complexes of N-cinnamoyl phenyl hydroxylamine (NCPHA) at various acid concentrations. Moreover, as NCPHA is more basic than N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxylamine (NBPFA), it forms more sensitive and stable complexes. Molar absorptivity of Ti-NCPHA complex at 8N HCl, i.e., 1.02×10^4 can be compared with those of a few most sensitive reported reagents for titanium, e.g., salicyl fluoro-¹⁴ ($\epsilon=9.2 \times 10^4$), 1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-Naphthol¹⁵ ($\epsilon=1.74 \times 10^4$) and Xylenol orange¹⁶ ($\epsilon=1.2 \times 10^4$). The present study has revealed the formation of 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) complex in the acidity range extending from pH 0.5 to 2.5N, and also 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 complexes at the acidity ranges of 3-5N and 7.5-9N HCl respectively. The existence of complexes having such compositions has been confirmed from data, obtained from measurements of absorbances of yellow coloured complexes at 410 nm, by Job's and molar ratio methods. These findings have been corroborated from evaluation and comparison of stepwise and overall formation constants by extended Yatsimirskii's¹⁴, Leden¹⁵ and Harvey-Manning's¹⁶ methods. An electronic and scientific computer (IBM 1130) was utilized for solution of a fourth degree polynomial equation to yield the formation constants of 1 : 3 metal to ligand systems following Yatsimirskii's method. The molar absorptivity, sensitivity, optimum range and the influence of

diverse ions on absorbance readings have been considered while examining the suitability of the reagent for extractive photometric determination of trace amounts of titanium.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions : Starting from A. R. grade potassium titanyl oxalate, a stock solution of titanium (2.18 mg/ml) was prepared and standardized¹⁷. Metal solutions of different strengths for successive experiments were obtained after proper dilution of the stock solution with twice distilled water. The reagent, NCPHA (*m.p.* 160-161°) was prepared following the method of Shome¹⁸. Standard reagent solutions of desired strength was prepared by dissolving the required amount in chloroform (A.R.). Other chemicals used in all spectrophotometric measurements were of A.R. or spectrograde quality.

Apparatus : A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with matched 1.0 cm glass cells was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

The pH of the solutions were recorded with a Cambridge pH meter (Bench type).

IBM 1130 scientific and electronic computer, using FORTRAN Programming, was employed for evaluation of the formation constants of 1 : 3 system.

Extraction procedure : An aliquot of titanium solution was taken in a 50 ml beaker and

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finally transferred into a 100 ml separatory funnel after being adjusted to desired acidity. A desired amount of the reagent solution (0.04 M) in chloroform was added to the aqueous layer. The volumes of the aqueous and nonaqueous phase were kept equal to 15 ml in all the cases. The two layers were shaken thoroughly for 15 minutes to reach equilibrium. The yellow coloured nonaqueous layer was then drained out in a 50 ml beaker containing anhydrous sodium sulphate. The process was repeated after addition of a 5 ml portion of chloroform to the aqueous phase. The combined extract, after drying over sodium sulphate, was diluted with chloroform to 25 ml in a volumetric flask. The absorbances of the solutions, thus prepared, were measured at 410 nm.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum: The absorbance spectra of solution of the complex (Ti=12 ppm), formed at 2N HCl, measured in the wavelength region 350-500 nm shows maximum absorption at 410 nm. Similar measurements for the complexes (Ti=4 ppm) formed at 4N and 8N HCl show the wavelength of maximum absorbance to be 402 nm in both the cases. As the reagent absorbs to a lesser extent at 410 nm, all other measurements were performed at 410 nm against the reagent blank. Fig. 1

represents the spectral curves of Ti-NCPHA complexes at 2N, 4N and 8N HCl against the reagent blank and of NCPHA (10 ml) against solvent blank. NCPHA has almost same absorption at 2N and 4N HCl.

Effect of reagent concentration: The metal was extracted at 2N, 4N and 8N HCl respectively with varying concentrations of the reagent. From the results, it was found that 8 ml, 6 ml and 4 ml of 0.04M NCPHA solution in chloroform were necessary for maximum colour development and quantitative extraction on a single operation at the respective acidities. The colour of the complexes was stable for about 4 hours.

Effect of acid on composition of the complexes

NCPHA complexes of titanium are extractable into chloroform from pH 0.5 to 10N HCl. The colour of the complex solutions is yellow. The complexes are extracted also into isoamyl alcohol, but the colour intensity is slightly lesser in the latter solvent. Measurements of absorbances of different sets of complementary solutions (Job's method) at 410 nm have revealed the predominance of 1:1 (metal: ligand) complex in the acidity range extending from pH 0.5 to 2.5N HCl. The result is supplemented from data by molar ratio method. Similar measurements at the same wavelength have shown that the

Fig. 1. Spectral curves of Ti-NCPHA complexes against reagent blank and those of NCPHA against solvent blank.

1. Absorbance of Ti-NCPHA complexes at 2NHCl (Ti=12 ppm)
2. Absorbance of Ti-NCPHA complex at 4NHCl (Ti=4 ppm)
3. Absorbance of Ti-NCPHA complex at 8NHCl (Ti=4 ppm)
4. Absorbance of NCPHA at 2N and 4NHCl.
5. Absorbance of NCPHA at 8N HCl.
R=10 ml. of 0.04M in all the cases.

complexes are predominantly 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 in the acidity range of 3.5*N* HCl and 7.5-9*N* HCl respectively. For other measurements, 2*N*, 4*N*, and 8*N* acids were used for 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 metal ligand systems. Figs. 2 and 3 represent the results of one of a few sets of the experiments.

Fig. 2. Job's plot

1. Ti-NCPHA complex at 2*N* HCl ; $M=R=2.116 \times 10^{-3}M$
2. Ti-NCPHA complex at 4*N* HCl ; $M=R=1.904 \times 10^{-3}M$
3. Ti-NCPHA complex at 8*N* HCl ; $M=R=2.646 \times 10^{-3}M$

Fig. 3. Molar Ratio plot.

1. Ti-NCPHA complex at 2*N* HCl ; $M=R=3.175 \times 10^{-3}M$.
 2. Ti-NCPHA complex at 4*N* HCl ; $M=R=9.520 \times 10^{-3}M$.
 3. Ti-NCPHA complex at 8*N* HCl ; $M=R=1.587 \times 10^{-3}M$.
- Metal taken = 1 ml in each case

Calibration curve, optimum range and photometric error : Measurements of absorbances of a series of complex solutions, extracted according to given procedure incorporating varied amounts of titanium, were carried out at 410 nm against the reagent blank. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration ranges 1-16 ppm, 0.5-7 ppm and 0.25-6 ppm at 2*N*, 4*N* and 8*N* HCl respectively.

The optimum concentration ranges following

Ringbom's curve were 2-6 ppm at 2*N* and 4*N* HCl and 0.8-4 ppm at 8*N* HCl.

The relative analysis error per one percent absolute photometric error according to Ayre's equation was found to be 2.72 in all the cases.

Molar absorptivity and sensitivity : The molar absorptivity of the complexes, calculated from Beer's law data at 410 nm, are $(1.60 \pm 0.02) \times 10^3$, $(5.06 \pm 0.04) \times 10^3$ and $(9.82 \pm 0.06) \times 10^3$ lit. mole⁻¹cm⁻¹ at 2*N*, 4*N* and 8*N* HCl respectively. The corresponding value at the respective λ_{max} are 1.60×10^3 (410 nm), 5.27×10^3 (400 nm) and 1.02×10^4 lit. mole⁻¹cm⁻¹ (400 nm). The molar absorptivity value at 4*N* and 8*N* HCl can be compared with those of a few reported highly sensitive reagents, e.g., salicyl fluorone¹⁹, 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2 Naphthol²⁰, xylenol orange¹⁹ (stated earlier) and a few ternary systems like Tribromopyrogallol and diantipyryl methane²¹ (ca. $\epsilon=157 \times 10^4$), Indoferron and 1, 3-diphenyl guanidium cation²² ($\epsilon=1.8 \times 10^4$), NBPFA and NH₄SCN,²³ ($\epsilon=1.54 \times 10^4$). The Sandell's sensitivity are 0.029 μ g per cm², 0.0095 and 0.0033 μ g per cm² at the respective acidities.

Effect of diverse ions : The absorbances of a series of Ti-NCPHA complex solutions, in presence of various ions, at different acid concentrations were measured at 410 nm. The effect of commonly associated ions in lower concentrations were found to lie within tolerable limits. The ions having appreciable interference in absorbance measurements included Fe(III), U(VI), V(V), Mo(VI), W(VI). The effect of Sn(IV) and Zr(IV) in moderate concentrations, were found to lie within tolerable limits. At higher acidity, only Fe(III) and V(V) interfere seriously. Considering this and also the molar absorptivity and sensitivity values of 1 : 3 complex at 8*N* HCl, the determination of trace amounts of Ti(IV) is recommended at 8*N* HCl.

Formation constants of the complexes

Yatsimirskii's method of graphical extrapolation and also that of Leden were utilized for evaluation of stepwise formation constants of different complex systems. The equilibrium ligand concentrations and the degree of complex formation were calculated from Beer's law data. The construction of suitable functions and their evaluation were made in the manner stated earlier²⁴.

For 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 systems, the stepwise and overall formation constants were calculated following each of the above methods.

Following Yatsimirskii's method of graphical extrapolation for 1 : 3 complex system, the stepwise formation constants (K_1 , K_2 and K_3) are related to different functions, constructed from experimental data, by the following equations :

$$a_1 = \epsilon_1 K_1$$

$$b_1 = \epsilon_3$$

$$a_2 = \epsilon_2 K_1 K_2 - \epsilon_1 K_1^2 \quad b_2 = \frac{\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1}{K_2}$$

$$a_3 = \epsilon_3 K_1 K_2 K_3 - \epsilon_1 K_1^3 \quad b_3 = \frac{\epsilon_3 - \epsilon_1}{K_3}$$

The above equations were converted into a suitable fourth degree polynomial equation in K_2 . It was solved on a IBM 1130 scientific and electronic computer based on FORTRAN Programming. The initial guess value of K_2 was supplied following the Newton-Raphson method. The results for all the systems along with the values of overall stability constants by Harvey-Manning's method are compiled in the Table 1.

ved stability of Ti-NCPHA complexes in comparison to the complexes of other analogous reagents²⁷. This is further evident from the fact that quantitative extraction of Ti-NCPHA complexes may be effected with lower concentrations of the reagent in comparison to other reagents.

The data from Table 1 and the preceding information suggest that the formulae of 1:1 and 1:2 complex may be represented as [TiORCL] and [TiOR₂] respectively, where HR stands for NCPHA.

For 1:3 system, the ratio was established by Job's and molar ratio methods and three stepwise formation constants were obtained by Yatsimirskii's method. But Leden's method yielded only two stepwise constant values (K_1 and K_2) as the plot of ψ

TABLE-1 STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANT^T FOR TITANIUM COMPLEXES AT 27±2°C.

Method	For 1:1 (Metal : Ligand) log K	For 1:2			For 1:3			
		log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	
Yatsimirskii's	2.60	2.61	2.75	5.36	4.17	4.02	4.53	12.72
Leden's	2.51	2.04	3.39	5.43	4.82	4.24	—	—
Harvey-Manning's	2.51	—	—	5.31	—	—	—	13.58

It is evident from the formula of the isolated complexes^{25,26} that titanium exists in solution in the form of TiO²⁺ in the pH as well as the normality range of acidity.

The structure of the ligand suggests that increased basicity of N atom of the ligand (compared to that of N in NBPFA) results from decreased inductive effect of >C=O group due to supply of electrons from nearby double bond and finally leads to impro-

against [L] led to a straight line parallel to abscissa. Therefore the probable formula of the complex is [TiOR₂]HR. This suggests that two ligand molecules are directly ligand linked to titanium and the third one is simply associated with the complex. Further the ligand molecules may be in resonance in such a way that always two ligands attack titanium as bidentate units and the association of third one is materialised through hydrogen bonding to titanyl oxygen.

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